

Deliverable 1.6

Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: 2-AGES

Contributing partners: 36-INSA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP1.6
WP and task	WP1, JRP15-R2-WP1-T3
Leader	2-AGES
Other contributors	36-INSA
Due month of the deliverable	M52
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Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC, other Save date: 10-June-22
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU <i>See updated Grant Agreement</i>
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input type="checkbox"/> WHO <input type="checkbox"/> OIE <input type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP1.6 (WP1-T3)

Introduction

After an initial postponement, there was an interim meeting held in Lisbon in April 2020.

Description of deliverable

The first in-person progress meeting after the kick-off meeting in 2020 was held over two days in Lisbon. Overall, it was a very constructive and successful meeting including all WPs and fostering inter-WP exchange and scientific discourse after two years of online collaboration. The meeting was a hybrid event (online and onsite) organized by INSA. Each WP presented the results obtained to date in plenary sessions. In addition, separate meetings were held for each WP, where the strategy to be followed in the final phase of the project was discussed, especially with regard to data analysis, data exchange, publications and other project outputs.

The onsite meeting included a social dinner also organized by INSA, and where participants were able to continue the scientific dialogue in a more relaxed atmosphere.

Agenda

**FED-AMR
Consortium meeting
April 21st - 22nd, 2022**

One Health EJP - FED-AMR

Grant Agreement number 773830

Attendees: the full FED-AMR Consortium, Members of the Advisory Board

About the meeting:

This is a meeting of the FED-AMR Consortium. It takes place in Lisbon, Portugal with the option to join online.

Online:

April 21st-22nd TEAMS – [Click here to join the meeting](#) – April 21st and April 22nd (morning and afternoon)

Face-to-face:

Location:

Room Pardal Monteiro (2Dg2), 2nd floor
Instituto Nacional de Saúde Doutor Ricardo Jorge (INSA)
Avenida Padre Cruz, 1649-046 Lisboa, Portugal
Tel. +351 217 519 246
Website: <https://www.insa.min-saude.pt/>

Plan your journey to reach INSA by:

- Taxi ((consider it can take ~20 minutes): it will cost around 15€.
- Metro (consider it can take ~40 minutes from Oriente station) - suggested directions: take the metro from Oriente/Cabo Ruivo/Olivais (red line) to Alameda (São Sebastião direction). Here change to green line: from Alameda to Campo Grande (Telheiras direction). INSA is within walking distance from Campo Grande metro, though you can ride the buses 767, 778 or 44B from the metro to the Institute (1 stop difference).

<https://www.google.com/maps/place/Instituto+Nacional+de+Sa%C3%BAde+Doutor+Ricardo+Jorge/@38.7648269,-9.1639443,15z/data=!4m5!3m4!1s0x0:0x3e892163f63ddc03!8m2!3d38.7648269!4d-9.1639443>

Times of the agenda follow the Central European Time zone.

The meeting will not be recorded.

Before the meeting:

All speakers send to the @WPLeader and @Manuela slides with the update of the status of the activities, deliverables, and plans in 2022 and to 2023. This is important to WP1 in order to follow the advancement of the works.

Each WP leader is responsible for organizing and coordinating the work during the time allocated to the respective WP, ensuring the involvement of all participants.

WP Leaders are responsible for arranging minutes of all WP sessions.

April 21st – Thursday

09.00-09.30	Reception and coffee
09.30-09.45	Welcome Dr. Fernando de Almeida, Dr ^a Cristina Abreu Santos (Executive Board, INSA) Werner Ruppitsch (FED-AMR Coordinator, AGES) Manuela Caniça (FED-AMR Deputy Leader, INSA)
09.45-09.50	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Approval of the agenda• Practical information
09.50-10.00	<u>WP 1</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Communications: Krista Rathammer, Karin Rainer
10.00-11.00	<u>WP 2</u> Results about: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Results of WGS: Adriana Cabal (30')• Bioinformatic pipeline for MGE: Solveig S. Mo (10')• Antimicrobial susceptibility testing: Tanel Tenson, Marwa Hassan, Manuela Caniça, Adriana Cabal (20')
11.00-11.15	Coffee Break
11.15-13.20	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Metagenomics: 16S: Daniel Olivença (30')• Metagenomics: AMR genes: Manuela Caniça (10')• Tools for metagenomics / Plan for linking ARG / Competence genes: Alexandre de Menezes (35')• Bacterial transformation: Markus Woegerbauer (20')• Discussion
13.40-14.50	Lunch Break
14.55-16.35	<u>WP 3</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Overview and interim results: Mónica Oleastro, Søren Persson, Ines Dost, Sven Maurischat, Anissa Scholtzek (1h30')• Discussion
16.30-17.30	<u>WP 4</u> Results about: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Heavy metals: Monica Felipe-Sotelo (20')• Antibiotics: Anna Gajda (20')• Herbicides: Martin Brandtner (20')• Discussion
19.00-22.00	Social dinner: <i>Restaurante-Bar Pharmacia Felicidade</i> (Rua de Santa Catarina n 2 e n, 4, 1249-069 Lisboa)

April 22nd – Friday

09.00-09.30 Reception and coffee

09.30-10.15 [WP 5](#)

- Results of WP5: Marwa Hassan and Mark Chambers (45')
- Discussion

10.15-10.45 [WP 6](#)

- Results of WP5: Brian Gardner, Giovanni Lo Iacono (30')

10.45-10.50 Coffee Break

10.50-11.50 (cont) (1.00h)

- Discussion

11.50-12.15 [WP 1](#)

- Other Communications
- Upcoming appointments and deadlines
- Outcomes

12.15-13.30 Lunch Break

13.30-14.30 [General discussion and next steps](#)

14.30-15.30 [Closure of the Consortium meeting](#)
